

SSHOC'n Tell Challenge

User Story

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League of Data as a teaser for a data management training

Trying out

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What

When inviting data supporters and researchers for a data management training, it would be great if we could make them aware of basic knowledge around archiving and publishing research data and the overview presented in the Data Management Expert Guide. For this purpose I will have a closer look at the League of Data game. Basically the game should be fun and not raise questions, but already show how a researcher profits from data management. It is very relevant for my daily work as I am involved in organising training events.

Who

I'm coordinator Training and Consultancy at the Data Archiving and Networked Services and was involved in creating the Data Management Expert Guide for CESSDA.

How

Play the LoD game and focus on: how straightforward it is to play; what benefits it highlights for a researcher to put effort in data management, archiving and publishing. It would be best if I could test it as a teaser for training with a couple of data supporters, but that option might be available in a couple of weeks. The issue here is also how knowledgeable the trainees already are. And I think we should not take it too serious, just a manner to steer them towards available resources like the Data Management Expert Guide.

When

The plan is to integrate the LoD game as a teaser to some of our training events.

Try the Game

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